

Unlocking the Value of Canada's Research Data

March 31, 2026

V 1.0 – Draft for Community Feedback

Digital Research
Alliance of Canada

Alliance de recherche
numérique du Canada

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Document Version History

Version	Date	Notes
0.7	February 2026	Shared for internal review (Digital Research Alliance of Canada)
1.0	March 2026	Publication version for community feedback

About Document Versions

This position paper describes the vision the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (the Alliance) has for how research data is safeguarded as a national asset. Realizing this vision requires broad engagement across Canada’s research ecosystem and the adoption of shared principles and approaches by researchers, institutions, service providers, and infrastructure operators.

Version 1.0, which is being released for public commentary, describes how shared infrastructure, national services, and domain expertise could work together to maximize the value of research data for Canadians. Feedback from the research community and other stakeholders will inform subsequent revisions, with an updated version planned for Summer–Fall 2026.

Executive Summary

The rapid technological advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and computational capacity are revolutionizing research across fields and sectors. The resulting global competition for talent and data to take advantage of these capabilities is reshaping how nations invest in research and innovation as well as expectations for maximizing return on investment (ROIs) of publicly funded research. In this regard, Canada is at a turning point. To deliver on national aspirations and remain competitive internationally, researchers from coast to coast to coast must be able to access and reuse the vast richness of Canadian data to drive innovation and discovery. Yet Canada's current research data landscape remains fragmented and faces challenges such as institutional capacity, scalability, and infrastructure and research software dependencies. These constraints reduce return on public investment by increasing duplication, slowing collaboration, and limiting the reuse of data for high-impact, interdisciplinary, AI-enabled research.

Canada has important strengths to build on, including national repositories, discovery services, research software platforms, and institutional data stewardship initiatives that support research data throughout the research lifecycle. However, these initiatives do not yet provide the level of interoperability and coordination required to fulfill some of the major national strategies and ambitions.

This position paper outlines how the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (the Alliance), its partners, and the broader digital research infrastructure community can collectively meet these challenges to optimize the management, reuse, and AI-readiness of research data in Canada. It provides a brief overview of the research data landscape and proposes how the Canadian Research Data Platform (CRDP) can leverage shared infrastructure, national services, and domain expertise to maximize the value of research data for Canadians. Community feedback will be incorporated into future versions of the paper.

The Canadian Research Data Platform (CRDP) aims to address current challenges by establishing a federated, nationally coordinated “system of systems” that connects shared infrastructure, services, and domain-led data spaces. The CRDP will reduce fragmentation, support data stewardship throughout the research lifecycle, and make national investments in data and infrastructure more effective by complementing (not replacing) institutional and disciplinary leadership. It will do so through:

- **National shared digital research infrastructure:** dependable, continuously available storage and compute (beyond traditional HPC), as well as trusted identity and access, secure data transfer, and baseline security capabilities that others can build on.
- **National shared services:** operational functions (e.g., monitoring, allocation, ticketing, and user support) and research support (e.g., research data management guidance, training, and AI-enhanced tooling) to provide equitable, effective services across regions and institutions.
- **Domain-specific approaches and National Data Spaces:** trusted, community-led environments that integrate data, services, and governance responsive to disciplinary needs

while aligning with national and international frameworks for data interoperability and stewardship.

- **Data for AI-enabled research:** improved machine-readability, machine-actionability, and explicit usage controls to support efficient, innovative, and responsible data (re)use

For researchers, the CRDP will support streamlined workflows, enhanced data management and reuse, Tri-Agency alignment, and greater collaboration across disciplines, institutions, and sectors. For institutions and academic libraries, the CRDP will provide a coordinated framework that reinforces local stewardship initiatives, enhances storage and compute capacity, and promotes new pathways for research data discovery, stewardship, and training.

Moving from vision to delivery, the CRDP will require coordination to bring together digital research infrastructure and service delivery partners, funders, institutions, academic libraries, researchers, and Indigenous partners. While this work is already under way, much work remains to be done to identify, synthesize, and act on shared values and priorities. To this end, the CRDP approach outlined in this paper is intended to be iterative: advancing through pilots and institutional efforts, refinement of governance and operating frameworks in consultation with partners, and improved interoperability and reuse across the research data lifecycle.

Introduction

High-quality, accessible data are the foundation of modern world-class research. Well-managed, high-quality data enable sharing and reuse, maximize return on investment (ROI), drive further discovery, and result in greater research impact and societal change. However, as modern research evolves in response to the broader adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the massive models and datasets underpinning it, issues in data quality, privacy, and sovereignty also demand new approaches to research, digital infrastructure, and policy.

In today's era of generative AI and large language models (LLMs), the goal of data-producing processes is oftentimes completely divorced from the potential future uses of the data. In this new context, data used by researchers must increasingly be prepared for reuse not only by humans, but also by machines. This shift has important implications for research data management (i.e., how research data are collected, documented, stored, governed, and made interoperable) and how researchers and machines find data, access them, and reuse them under appropriate conditions.¹

The importance of high-quality and interoperable data was highlighted during the COVID-19 pandemic, when the lack of interoperability,² inaccessible or missing data,³ and incomplete or absent metadata⁴ delayed the collective understanding of the rapidly evolving pandemic. More generally, the rapid and broad adoption of AI to identify patterns or train models provides another example of the importance of well-managed, high-quality data for research: without good data, even strong machine learning methods will underperform, amplify biases, or produce unreliable findings.⁵

The underlying economics of research data are also changing. While the cost per unit for producing, storing, and using data is decreasing, overall costs related to stewarding data (e.g., storage and compute infrastructure, software, skilled personnel, and long-term governance) are increasing due to intensifying compute needs and exponential increases in the volume of data produced. These budgetary considerations are amplified by AI in research contexts, where demand for large and ideally well-curated datasets places new pressures on data

¹ To learn more about Research Data Management (RDM) and the Alliance's RDM services, see <https://www.alliancecan.ca/en/our-services/research-data-management>.

² Greene, D. N., McClintock, D. S., & Durant, T. J. S. (2021). Interoperability: COVID-19 as an Impetus for Change. *Clinical Chemistry*, 67(4), 592–595. <https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/hvab006>

³ Pham, H.-T., Do, T., Baek, J., Nguyen, C.-K., Pham, Q.-T., Nguyen, H. L., et al. (2024). Handling Missing Data in COVID-19 Incidence Estimation: Secondary Data Analysis. *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance*, 10, e53719. <https://doi.org/10.2196/53719>

⁴ Maxwell, L., Shreedhar, P., Dauga, D., McQuilton, P., Terry, R. F., Denisiuk, A., et al. (2023). FAIR, ethical, and coordinated data sharing for COVID-19 response: a scoping review and cross-sectional survey of COVID-19 data sharing platforms and registries. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 5(10), e712–e736. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-7500\(23\)00129-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-7500(23)00129-2)

⁵ See, for example, Noble, S. U. (2018). *Algorithms of oppression: How search engines reinforce racism*. NYU Press.; D'Ignazio, C., & Klein, L. F. (2020). *Data feminism*. MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11805.001.0001>; Richardson, A. (2022). Biased data lead to biased algorithms. *CMAJ*, 194(9), E341. <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.80860>; Nazer L.H., Zatarah R., Waldrip S., Ke J.X.C., Moukheiber M., Khanna A.K., et al. (2023) Bias in artificial intelligence algorithms and recommendations for mitigation. *PLoS Digit Health* 2(6): e0000278. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000278>; Wald, B. (2024). *First Nations and artificial intelligence*. Chiefs of Ontario. https://chiefs-of-ontario.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/2024_08_16_RP_First_Nations_and- AI_Paper_BW_final_Ack.pdf

documentation, access controls, and the ability to move data securely across systems. In this environment, gaps in stewardship and interoperability translate directly into inefficiencies: duplicated data collection, repeated cleaning and reformatting, delays in collaboration, and missed opportunities for (re)use.

These trends are now shaping national approaches to research infrastructure and data policy worldwide. Rather than treating data as an output managed at the end of a project, leading jurisdictions are building coordinated frameworks that strengthen the full research data lifecycle. Europe's Data Union Strategy,⁶ for example, positions the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to strengthen interoperability across research domains and improve data discovery to support reuse, whereas the Digital Europe Programme⁷ includes over €74 million for sectoral data spaces and €30 million to advance edge-to-cloud integration.⁸ In areas such as health data, considerable funding has been dedicated to initiatives such as the European Health Data Space (€810 million)⁹ and the UK's health data research service (£600 million).¹⁰ These efforts aim to make large pools of high-quality data available for reuse under appropriate governance, strengthen interoperability, and enable advances such as domain-tailored AI models and data-driven breakthroughs that benefit researchers, public administrations, and the economy.

What is the current state in Canada?

Canada's research ecosystem is increasingly defined by the scale, diversity, and long-term value of the data it produces. Across disciplines, researchers now generate and share data at volumes and complexities that exceed what existing infrastructure and practices were ever designed to support. From genomics sequences and climate simulations to transcribed texts and images of artwork, modern research routinely produces terabytes to petabytes or even exabytes of data that require not only storage, but also robust stewardship, metadata, secure access, and mechanisms for long-term (re)use. The result is growing pressure on a research data landscape that was built incrementally and locally, and that now struggles to sustain the demands placed on it by emerging national priorities.

These pressures are not abstract. They sit at the core of Canada's most ambitious national priorities from genomics and health to Artificial Intelligence, freshwater and climate adaptation—

⁶ European Commission. (2025). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: Data Union Strategy unlocking data for AI* (COM/2025/835 final). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2025:835:FIN>

⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme>

⁸ For more about edge-to-cloud computing, see, for example, <https://www.scalecomputing.com/resources/edge-to-cloud-computing-integration>.

⁹ <https://www.ehtel.eu/media-room/latest-news/186-european-health-data-space-insights-into-savings-financing-and-governance.html>

¹⁰ <https://wellcome.org/insights/articles/national-data-service-will-simplify-access-health-data-research>

all of which depend on data that are aligned with FAIR principles for data management,¹¹ responsibly governed, and sustainably supported. Yet Canada's current research data ecosystem, built organically over decades through local as well as grant-funded initiatives, project-based platforms, and varied disciplinary practices, cannot consistently meet these expectations. Coordinated, sustainable funding and governance are needed to bring this ecosystem into closer alignment both with individual and national aspirations.

National ambitions outpace a fragmented landscape

Several federal strategies increasingly articulate objectives that cannot be achieved without interoperable, high-quality, ethically governed, and consistently stewarded data.

Freshwater, Environmental Monitoring, and Climate Modelling

The National Freshwater Data Strategy¹² requires unified discovery layers, harmonized metadata, and standardized vocabularies so that federal, provincial, territorial, Indigenous, academic, and community datasets can be synthesized. But freshwater and environmental data remain highly fragmented: multiple custodians, inconsistent formats, limited discoverability, and non-aligned standards impede integrated modelling and policy analysis.

Climate-focused initiatives, including Canada's National Adaptation Strategy,¹³ face similar challenges with monitoring data spanning multiple repositories and formats, while modelling outputs cannot always be compared or reused because foundational metadata is missing or inconsistent.

Health Research and Health System Learning

The Pan-Canadian Health Data Strategy¹⁴ envisioned streamlined access to high-quality health data that also respects Indigenous data sovereignty and safeguards data pertaining to racialized as well as other vulnerable populations. In practice, though, sensitive data remain distributed across hospitals, universities, clinics, provincial custodians, and disease-specific platforms. Legal and operational fragmentation makes integration extremely challenging.

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

¹² Canada Water Agency. (2025). *National Freshwater Data Strategy Workshop 2024 - Report* (Cat. No. En4-789/2024E-PDF). Government of Canada. <https://www.canada.ca/en/canada-water-agency/data-collaboration/national-freshwater-data-strategy/workshop-2024/workshop-2024-report.html>

¹³ Environment and Climate Change Canada. (2023). *Canada's National Adaptation Strategy: Building resilient communities and a strong economy* (Cat. No. En4-544/2023E-PDF). Government of Canada. https://publications.gc.ca/collections/collection_2023/eccc/en4/En4-544-2023-eng.pdf

¹⁴ See the following Public Health Agency of Canada reports published between 2021 and 2022: *Expert Advisory Group Report 1: Charting a Path toward Ambition* (<https://www.canada.ca/en/public-health/corporate/mandate/about-agency/external-advisory-bodies/list/pan-canadian-health-data-strategy-reports-summaries/expert-advisory-group-report-01-charting-path-toward-ambition.html>); *Expert Advisory Group Report 2: Building Canada's Health Data Foundation* (<https://www.canada.ca/en/public-health/corporate/mandate/about-agency/external-advisory-bodies/list/pan-canadian-health-data-strategy-reports-summaries/expert-advisory-group-report-02-building-canada-health-data-foundation.html>); and *Expert Advisory Group Report 3: Toward a world-class health data system* (<https://www.canada.ca/en/public-health/corporate/mandate/about-agency/external-advisory-bodies/list/pan-canadian-health-data-strategy-reports-summaries/expert-advisory-group-report-03-toward-world-class-health-data-system.html>).

Artificial Intelligence

The Sovereign AI Compute Strategy¹⁵ clearly emphasizes the need for high-quality, well-governed data and data environments. AI models trained on fragmented or poorly curated data cannot support reliable research or responsible deployment.

These federal strategies are fundamentally data-dependent, but under the current conditions they are also data-constrained. A recent report prepared for Érudit and the Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN)¹⁶ underscores cross-cutting concerns regarding the lack of collaborative leadership, uneven implementation of data standards, infrastructure sustainability, and the need for more nuanced access controls for sensitive data of various kinds. To meet the aspirations articulated in these strategies, Canada requires a coordinated, durable, and interoperable research data ecosystem. Without such an ecosystem, the aims of each strategy may remain unattainable.

Operational realities of Research Data Management in Canada

National Multidisciplinary Repositories: Strengths and Limits

Canada has been a global leader in research data management, both in developing best practices and supporting researchers in adopting them. Canadian academic libraries have played a crucial role in championing national shared infrastructure for research data. A central example of this effort is Borealis, a multidisciplinary research data repository supported by the Alliance in partnership with Scholars Portal and regional academic library consortia. Higher education institutions operate their own repository collections and services through Borealis to meet local data publication needs.

Borealis' model of shared responsibility has enabled over 80 institutional repositories to provide access to over 21,000 published datasets with digital object identifiers (DOIs) and common metadata, which improve interoperability and enable the integration of data into computational workflows—including those mediated by AI. These standardized datasets can then be harvested into Lunaris, Canada's national data discovery service, providing researchers with a single point of search across a wide range of Canadian repositories. This represents a significant investment in infrastructure and deep professional expertise that institutions, and libraries in particular, contribute to sustaining Canada's research data ecosystem.

Nonetheless, scaling institutional repositories to support very large datasets, often in the hundreds of gigabytes to terabytes, is technically and financially challenging as institutions must

¹⁵ Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada. (2024). *Canadian Sovereign AI Compute Strategy*. Government of Canada. <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/ised/en/canadian-sovereign-ai-compute-strategy>

¹⁶ Arbuckle, A. 2025. Digital Research Infrastructure for the HSS in Canada: An update landscape analysis. <https://apropos.erudit.org/infrastructure-hss-analysis/?lang=en>

absorb substantial long-term storage and infrastructure costs. The Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR) was designed to address these challenges and play a critical complementary role. It does so by supporting researchers working with very large datasets across disciplines and integrating directly with national advanced research computing (ARC) systems. Borealis and FRDR therefore provide researchers with Canadian-hosted national repository services to meet their needs, supporting data curation and addressing scalability challenges.

Specialized Repositories and Sustainability Challenges

Beyond multidisciplinary platforms like Borealis and FRDR, Canada hosts a rapidly growing ecosystem of specialized data repositories operated by research groups and disciplinary communities. These repositories are often endorsed and trusted within their domains, increasing the likelihood that their datasets will be discovered and reused. However, their long-term sustainability is uncertain. While a few have established enduring funding models, most rely on short-term project-based grants, including those from the Canada Foundation for Innovation (CFI) and the Tri-Agencies. These funding cycles do not align with the long-term nature of data preservation and create real risks of specialized repositories losing valuable research outputs if projects end or priorities shift.

National data infrastructure could provide a long-term, stable backbone for the preservation of domain-specific data that extends beyond the life of any particular project, institution, or funding cycle. And sustainable national infrastructure would ensure that data acquired with public funds remain accessible, curated, and reusable for decades. Infrastructure of this kind would also provide the technical resilience, redundancy, and governance infrastructure necessary to protect sensitive data, support regulatory compliance, and safeguard institutional and intellectual property.

Gaps in Active and Sensitive Data Sharing

Researchers frequently need to share data across collaborating teams and institutions. Today, sharing data effectively and appropriately remains a major challenge (e.g., as project data are collected, processed, or analyzed). Many institutions support their researchers with commercial cloud solutions such as Microsoft OneDrive, which can store data with a range of sensitivity levels, including protected health information (PHI) and personally identifiable information (PII). But the responsibility for correctly configuring privacy settings and access controls falls on individual researchers. This arrangement increases administrative burden and introduces risks related to data sensitivity, intellectual property, and secondary use. Furthermore, across domains or research communities, active research data—that is, data that is currently being processed, analyzed, or revised as part of ongoing research and is generally stored in easy-to-access locations rather than longer-term archives—can vary significantly in terms of size, file formats, access requirements, AI-readiness, and other factors. These differences can make sharing active data across systems even more difficult from multiple perspectives (e.g., researcher, data steward, systems administrator, IT support staff).

Sensitive data, especially clinical, genomic, and Indigenous health data, face even greater structural barriers. It is exceptionally difficult to integrate these data for research purposes

because—among other factors—PII and PHI are held by numerous custodians like hospitals, universities, and clinics, each of which must meet the legal and privacy requirements of their provincial jurisdictions. When dealing with Indigenous data, which may include health data or other sensitive data but requires wholly distinct governance considerations, it is essential that these entities also recognize and advance Indigenous data sovereignty by adhering to CARE¹⁷ and OCAP¹⁸ principles, for example, and co-develop data policies and protocols that support Indigenous data repatriation, self-government, and self-determination.

Addressing some of these needs around active and sensitive data, promising initiatives such as HPC4Health, SecureData4Health, Canadian Research Data Center Network (CRDCN), and GEMINI provide secure environments for social and clinical research and seek to enable inter-institutional sharing. Yet these initiatives also depend on short-term and multi-source funding (CFI, Tri-Agency, Alliance), which limits their ability to plan long-term or scale nationally.

Policy requirements and institutional burden

The Tri-Agency released its Research Data Management Policy¹⁹ to align Canadian RDM practices with global standards and improve the sharing, discoverability, and reuse of publicly funded research data. The policy required higher education institutions and research hospitals to publish institutional RDM strategies describing how they would steward agency-funded data. To date, 204 strategies have been released across universities, colleges, CÉGEPs, and research hospitals. Across institutions, two priorities consistently emerge:

Strengthening RDM practices by integrating libraries, research offices, and other support services; and

Providing RDM training for researchers through national providers such as the Alliance or through local institutional resources.

The Policy also will require researchers to submit data management plans (DMPs) with grant applications. The Alliance supports this requirement nationally through the DMP Assistant, which provides Policy-aligned templates developed with community partners. Some institutions have also created their own templates based on the national model. Finally, researchers will be required to deposit all research (meta)data and code that directly support publications arising from agency-funded research.

While the requirements of the Policy represent an essential step forward, they also create new pressures. Without adequate infrastructure and coordinated support, compliance may increase administrative burden and reduce research productivity. Compliance and successful adoption of

¹⁷ <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

¹⁸ <https://fnigc.ca/ocap-training/>

¹⁹ Canadian Institutes of Health Research, Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada, & Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada. (2021). *Tri-Agency research data management policy*. Government of Canada. <https://science.gc.ca/site/science/en/interagency-research-funding/policies-and-guidelines/research-data-management/tri-agency-research-data-management-policy>

such policies require more than just infrastructure and training. They also require changes in disciplinary norms and incentive structures. As more researchers begin depositing data, well-maintained repositories with strong curation support and training will become even more critical. Standardized, accessible RDM training will not only facilitate compliance but also promote innovation, enable interdisciplinary research, and help foster a stronger culture of open science in Canada.

The existing approach can no longer support Canada's ambitions

Historically, Canada's research data landscape grew from local needs and community innovation. This grassroots approach has produced valuable services and strong expertise distributed across institutions, but also a landscape characterized by duplication, uneven capacity, and misalignment between local and national solutions.

A recent report from the Office of the Chief Science Advisor²⁰ makes explicit the systemic issues in the Canadian data landscape. The report identifies inconsistencies in stewardship, unclear roles and responsibilities, gaps in cross-jurisdictional coordination, and the absence of coherent governance mechanisms that could align the numerous actors involved in Canada's research data ecosystem. It highlights the risks posed by short-term project funding, duplicative infrastructures, and the lack of common standards. Critically, it emphasizes that without integrated governance, Canada cannot realize the full benefits of open science, interdisciplinary research, Indigenous data sovereignty, or responsible AI, nor can it meet the expectations outlined in the country's major research and innovation strategies.

In the absence of coordinated approaches to research data, communities across domains have developed platforms and services tailored to their specific research needs. While these initiatives provide valuable capabilities for their respective communities, they have also contributed to fragmentation and duplication. Many platforms aim to address similar needs but do so using different standards, metadata practices, governance models, and sustainability approaches. As a result, they rarely interoperate, even when they support overlapping communities or rely on similar data. These platforms are also frequently funded independently rather than through coordinated investment. Greater clarity and coordination in funding approaches can help reduce unnecessary duplication while enabling existing platforms and expertise to interoperate and contribute more effectively to a coherent research data ecosystem.

The trajectory of human genomics in Canada illustrates how we can leverage national expertise and build a more unified, consolidated ecosystem. While the field has long faced fragmentation, the Pan-Canadian Genome Library (PCGL) shows what becomes possible when funders and communities act in a coordinated way. Initially supported through a \$15 million grant from the

²⁰ Office of the Chief Science Advisor. (2024). *Towards a national scientific data governance framework*. Government of Canada. <https://science.gc.ca/site/science/en/office-chief-science-advisor/open-science/data-governance/towards-national-scientific-data-governance-framework>

Canadian Institutes of Health Research, PCGL has created a shared framework for responsible data access, ethical governance, and federated search, and in doing so has brought a highly distributed community together around common expectations. Its success has enabled Genome Canada to position PCGL as a foundational element of their Precision Health Initiative—demonstrating that when funders align requirements and communities organize around shared principles, Canada can build data infrastructures that are coherent, scalable, and widely adopted.

PCGL also underscores the broader lesson: national objectives are achievable only when infrastructures, standards, and governance are aligned across communities and funders. The aims of Canada's major existing and future strategies cannot be met by isolated repositories, project-funded platforms, inconsistent metadata standards, or infrastructures that differ widely in capability and longevity. To succeed, Canada requires:

- Flexible yet interoperable data architectures across disciplines and jurisdictions
- Shared vocabularies and harmonized metadata
- Sustained, integrated storage and compute environments
- Mechanisms for secure active data sharing
- Coordinated governance and long-term stewardship models
- Training and support systems that connect local and national efforts

The Canadian Research Data Platform

Canada is at a turning point. As geopolitical conditions shift and international partnerships become less predictable, Canada's ability to sustain sovereign digital research infrastructure is increasingly central to innovation, talent development, and research aligned with national priorities. These ambitions, however, will remain out of reach as long as Canadian research data remains siloed, fragmented, and difficult to access and reuse at scale.

The Alliance has the mandate to coordinate, operate, and fund activities in advanced research computing, research data management, and research software in coordination with DRI partners and community members across the country. As such, the Alliance is uniquely positioned to lead a national effort that builds on Canada's strengths in data stewardship, mobilizes research excellence, and brings funders and partners together around shared approaches. This vision is shaping the Canadian Research Data Platform (CRDP): a nationally coordinated framework designed to connect the infrastructure, services, and standards needed to plan, manage, govern, and reuse research data across Canada.

The CRDP represents a coherent national approach that will bring together shared infrastructure, national services, and domain-specific practices to enable responsible data use and maximize the value of research data for Canada.

National Shared Digital Research Infrastructure

The CRDP creates an opportunity to build on Canada's strong foundation of digital research infrastructure and evolve toward a federated, nationally coordinated system that amplifies the value of existing and future investments.

At the core of this vision is national shared infrastructure that provides dependable, cross-cutting capabilities required across disciplines, institutions, and regions. While the Alliance already oversees national high-performance computing (HPC) systems delivered to common operational expectations, HPC alone is not sufficient to support the continuously available, data-centric, and service-oriented research workflows that now dominate many disciplines.

The CRDP will build on this foundation by extending national infrastructure beyond traditional HPC to also provide highly reliable, continuously available storage and compute. These capabilities will support data-intensive workflows, AI development, active data management, and sustained service delivery over time. Together, they will form a stable infrastructure layer on which the CRDP can be built.

This national shared infrastructure will also enable others to rely and build on it. Baseline capabilities such as trusted identity and access, secure data movement, and shared compute and storage environments reduce duplication and lower the operational burden on partner service providers, repositories, and domain platforms. This complementary relationship will allow institutions and other DRI partners to focus on their added-value services—including data curation, analytics, workflows, and research-facing applications—rather than on the most complex and expensive aspects of infrastructure operation.

This approach builds directly on existing national capabilities and investments. Canada has already established important national anchors for research infrastructure and data stewardship through coordinated national services, distributed host sites, and policy frameworks that emphasize interoperability, sustainability, and responsible data use. The CRDP will align and extend these efforts by connecting infrastructure, governance, and operations into a coherent national layer while allowing independently operated platforms and services to integrate where national provision is neither feasible nor necessary. In doing so, the CRDP will strengthen the overall resilience, reach, and impact of Canada's digital research ecosystem.

National Shared Services

While infrastructure provides the foundation, services ensure that researchers, platforms, and institutions can access, trust, and effectively use that infrastructure across organizational and jurisdictional boundaries. National shared services thus translate national infrastructure into usable, reliable research capability, available to researchers across Canada regardless of institutional affiliation or research domain.

Within the CRDP, national shared services are envisioned as a common layer of operational and enabling functions that support consistent access, security, and reliability across national

shared infrastructure, extending and interoperating more effectively with services already offered at the institutional, regional, and national level. These services include identity and access management, security monitoring and incident response, resource allocation and accounting, service monitoring, and cross-platform user support. Together with user support, RDM, and training, these services would enable researchers and platforms to make efficient and effective use of national shared infrastructure.

National shared services must also address persistent gaps in institutional capacity. While many institutions and regions have developed strong local services, including those focused around institutional repositories, capacity and expertise remain uneven—particularly for smaller institutions and emerging research communities. Significant gaps also persist related to awareness, knowledge, and training around RDM; support for CARE and OCAP principles and their integration into existing services, training, and research workflows; equitable recognition and legitimation of data practices across disciplinary and other contexts; and issues related to who can access data or who benefits most from its reuse. Addressing such issues will involve ongoing communication and coordination, as well as responsive solutions to leverage the expertise of academic librarians, data stewards, service providers, researchers, and others invested in this work. By providing shared services that are difficult to sustain locally, and by creating new pathways to connect institutional and national services, the CRDP aims to reduce duplication and help ensure that essential capabilities and related upskilling opportunities offered by the Alliance and its partners²¹ are available across the research ecosystem. As academic libraries and Canadian researchers navigate new challenges caused by ongoing and expected shifts in technological, operational, and institutional realities, the CRDP will also create opportunities for reflection on the value and potential futures of existing national services.

In this context, national shared services can strengthen research data practices and support the transition to more data-intensive and AI-enabled research. Services that support data planning, organization, metadata, controlled access, discovery, stewardship, and active management of data during the research process would improve data quality, consistency, and reuse across the research lifecycle. Delivered through national coordination, these services would also provide a consistent foundation for advanced analytics and AI while complementing institutional systems and repositories.

National shared services will also be designed to complement local and domain-specific services delivery rather than replace them. Institutions, regions, and domain initiatives would be able to rely on national services for broadly applicable functions while focusing local effort on areas of differentiation and expertise. In doing so, the CRDP would help ensure that national infrastructure investments translate into sustained, equitable, and interoperable research capability across Canada.

²¹ <https://explora.alliancecan.ca/>

Domain-Specific Approaches and National Data Spaces

Together, national infrastructure and shared services provide a usable, reliable foundation, but effective data integration must ultimately be grounded in research practice. Many of the challenges associated with data reuse, interoperability, and responsible access are domain-specific, shaped by disciplinary norms, governance models, training pathways, and trust relationships that cannot be addressed through horizontal or "one-size-fits-all" solutions alone.

Within the CRDP, National Data Spaces are envisioned as trusted, domain-driven environments that bring together data, services, governance, and community engagement within a coherent national context. Data spaces represent a transformative paradigm shift in how research data is managed, moving from a fragmented approach along institutional, geographical or domain siloes to one that is federated and interconnected within and across research domains. Data spaces are not single, centralized platforms or repositories that address all research needs for a community or domain, but rather a collaboration and integration between the research community, infrastructure, and service providers (e.g., curation, data visitation, analysis, and visualization) that could include several entities working together. In this way, data spaces remain grounded in the needs, standards, and practices of specific research communities while still addressing the issues of fragmentation, interoperability, and reuse highlighted above.

This approach builds on Canada's strengths. Across domains such as health, genomics, environment, biodiversity, and the social sciences, research communities have developed shared data resources, standards, and governance arrangements tailored to their research contexts. National Data Spaces should provide a mechanism to connect and sustain these efforts, aligning them with national capabilities where appropriate while also respecting community leadership and domain-specific practices.

Additionally, National Data Spaces should enable clearer alignment between infrastructure, governance, and policy. Recent national discussions on research data governance—including work led by the Office of the Chief Science Advisor, the Canada Water Agency, the Canadian Institute for Health Information, and Genome Canada—emphasize the importance of interoperability, responsible data stewardship, and coordination at scale. National Data Spaces offer a practical way to operationalize these principles within specific domains, rather than applying them uniformly across the entire research ecosystem.

The Alliance's approach to building National Data Spaces will be iterative by design. Initial pilots are intended to explore how communities engage and can collaborate across disciplines and sectors, how governance models evolve, and how shared infrastructure and services are used in practice. In doing so, the Alliance aims to learn from other jurisdictions, such as Australia and Europe, where data spaces are also being tested in research contexts. Importantly, this approach is not intended to define a single model—or to be limited to initiatives based in the Global North—but rather to inform a Canadian approach that reflects the country's realities, diverse disciplinary cultures, and the shared interest of national, regional, and local partners in building an integrated research data ecosystem.

Data for AI-Enabled Research

The vision for the CRDP cannot be fulfilled if it is grounded in how research data used to be managed. It must be AI-ready, empowering its users to harness AI and machine learning affordances for responsible research and data management. While AI does not fundamentally change the importance of good data practices, it does require data to be structured, documented, and governed in ways that support automated analysis and responsible AI use effectively at scale. If unaddressed, this gap will significantly limit the impact of national investments in data, infrastructure, and AI altogether.

Within the CRDP, AI-enabled research would require shared capabilities and expectations that allow data to remain understandable to researchers and actionable by machines, under clear and auditable conditions. This should include support for machine-readable metadata, explicit usage conditions, provenance, and active data management practices integrated into the research process.

Convening around a shared vision

The CRDP provides an opportunity to anchor national efforts and to coalesce around a shared national vision for research data—one that has been frequently articulated but that now can be expressed through a common framework and delivered through coordinated action.

Realizing this opportunity will require collective engagement across the research ecosystem. It calls for funders to work more deliberately together to better coordinate investments in national digital research infrastructure, aligning priorities, reducing fragmentation, and ensuring that investments made through different programs and mechanisms contribute to a coherent and sustainable national system.

This vision also requires a shared effort to identify strategic research areas where data have national importance, where long-term stewardship is essential, and where the value of reuse should be maximized. In these cases, national coordination provides a way to enable scale, trust, and impact across institutions, regions, and disciplines without constraining domain leadership or innovation.

The CRDP provides a structured way to build on Canada's existing strengths. National and regional partners, institutions, and research communities have developed deep expertise, infrastructure, and governance models. To successfully power and promote a reuse-based approach to data, the CRDP will depend on, and need to work hand in hand with, many members of the broader research community. Both its vision and the work of implementing it must be shared. A nationally coordinated approach promises to reinforce and connect existing

efforts and expertise through shared infrastructure, services, and data spaces, so that we can collectively unlock the value of Canada's research data.